

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF PORTAL VEIN DUPLEX DOPPLER SONOGRAPHY IN ASSESSING LIVER CIRRHOSIS SEVERITY: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY KEEPING LIVER BIOPSY AS REFERENCE STANDARD

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Abstract

Objective:

To evaluate the diagnostic efficacy of portal vein Duplex Doppler parameters including portal vein diameter (PVD), portal vein peak systolic velocity (PSV), and portal venous flow orientation in assessing liver cirrhosis severity, using liver biopsy as the reference standard.

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Diagnostic Radiology, Capital Development Authority Hospital, CDA Islamabad, performed over six months following approval of synopsis from CPSP.

Methodology:

In a cross-sectional validation study using non-random consecutive sampling, 120 patients with suspected or confirmed liver disease underwent Doppler sonography and liver biopsy within two weeks. Portal vein diameter (PVD), peak systolic velocity (PSV), and flow direction was assessed. These factors were contrasted with histological grading of cirrhosis. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were computed. Data was analyzed using chi-square tests, logistic regression, and diagnostic performance metrics.

Results:

A PSV ≤ 15 cm/s showed the best diagnostic performance (sensitivity 85.9%, specificity 81.3%) ($p = 0.001$). PVD ≥ 13 mm had 79.5% sensitivity and 76.1% specificity ($p = 0.003$). Reversed/turbulent flow showed high specificity (89.5%) but lower sensitivity (61.9%) ($p = 0.017$). Logistic regression did not find a statistically significant association between Doppler parameters and biopsy staging. Portal vein PSV < 15 cm/s had an odds ratio of 0.67 (95% CI: 0.32–1.40, $p = 0.2868$) for predicting advanced liver disease.

Conclusion:

Portal vein Doppler ultrasound is a helpful, non-invasive tool for cirrhosis assessment but shows limited reliability in disease staging. Combining Duplex Doppler sonography with elastography or blood markers may improve diagnostic accuracy in resource-constrained environments like Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Liver cirrhosis, a leading cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide¹, presents significant diagnostic challenges in low-resource healthcare settings like Pakistan. As per the available global health data² and information from the Pakistan Medical Association, chronic hepatitis B and C remain predominant causes^{3, 4}, compounded by increasing rates of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) due to obesity and diabetes. Awareness and availability of treatment has improved, but still, late stage presentation and poor screening tools remain key challenges for timely diagnosis and management⁵. The need for reliable and non-invasive diagnostic tools that can be used in resource limited setups (like Pakistan) where expensive advanced diagnostic technologies are not commonly available, or their cost is prohibitive, is both immediate and clinically relevant^{6,7}.

Liver cirrhosis constitutes progressive liver scarring, surface nodularity, fibrous septa formation and structural alteration of normal liver parenchyma resulting in both portal hypertension and liver dysfunction⁸. The transition from compensated to decompensated cirrhosis comes with dramatic prognostic implications, so early identification and accurate staging of the disease is essential for determining management strategies and enhancing survival⁹. The high incidence rate of hepatitis C, driven by poor health care infrastructure, lack of routine screening, and the widespread use of non-sterilized needles is a well-documented problem¹⁰. Increasing obesity rates and diabetes have translated into a greater number of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease patients as well, making the liver disease landscape even more complicated¹¹. Early diagnosis and accurate staging of liver cirrhosis are critical for effective management; yet liver biopsy – the current gold standard¹² – is invasive, costly, and often unavailable in rural or peripheral hospitals¹³. As a result, there has been rising interest in non-invasive methods like Duplex Doppler sonography of the portal vein, which is a promising non-invasive and radiation free modality that evaluates hepatic hemodynamics in real time. Variations in portal

vein diameter (PVD), portal vein peak systolic velocity (PSV), and portal venous flow direction have been studied for their correlation with the severity of liver disease, presenting a possible substitute for histological grading¹⁴. However, reported diagnostic efficacy has been inconsistent across different studies and patient populations¹⁵. A 2020 study from Lahore, Pakistan demonstrated that reduced portal vein peak systolic velocity correlated with histologically confirmed cirrhosis, while a study in Karachi, Pakistan found portal vein diameter to be significantly increased in advanced scarring. Meanwhile, conflicting findings exist on the diagnostic value of hepatopetal versus hepatofugal portal venous flow, with some studies showing high specificity but low sensitivity. A 2022 meta-analysis pointed out inconsistencies in the threshold values and methods across different areas, highlighting the need for locally validated, standardized procedures¹⁶. Additionally, most existing studies have been carried out in tertiary care hospitals, leaving a significant knowledge gap regarding the use of these techniques in broader, low-resource healthcare environments where liver biopsy access is limited¹⁷.

This study aimed to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of Doppler ultrasound parameters—specifically PVD, PSV and flow orientation in determining the severity of liver cirrhosis using liver biopsy as the reference benchmark. The goal was to determine whether Doppler ultrasound could serve as a reliable, non-invasive alternative to biopsy in resource constrained environments. It is hypothesized that Doppler sonography indicators provide a reliable, non-invasive measurement of cirrhosis severity when compared to liver biopsy in the Pakistani population.

Methodology:

Study Design and Setting:

This cross-sectional validation study was conducted at the Department of Diagnostic Radiology, Capital Development Authority (CDA) Hospital, Islamabad, over a period of six

months after receiving approval of the outline from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP). The sampling method employed was non-random consecutive sampling. The framework was forward-looking observational in character.

Inclusion Criteria:

Adults aged 18 years and above
Clinical or biochemical suspicion of chronic liver disease
Underwent both Duplex Doppler ultrasound and liver biopsy within a two-week interval
Provided written informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

Known hepatocellular carcinoma
Portal vein thrombosis
Previous portosystemic shunt surgery
Incomplete biopsy or Doppler sonography records.

Sample Size Calculation:
Based on prior research by Al-Dabbagh et al. reporting a 84.2% sensitivity of Doppler ultrasound in cirrhosis detection. Using this figure ($p = 0.842$), with a confidence level of 95% ($\alpha = 0.05$), power of 80% ($\beta = 0.2$), and absolute precision of 7%, a sample size of 120 patients was calculated using PASS version 15 software.

Data Collection and Imaging Protocol:

Doppler studies were performed using a high-resolution ultrasound device (GE Logiq P9, GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA). Parameters assessed included:

Portal vein diameter PVD (≥ 13 mm = abnormal)
Portal vein PSV (≤ 15 cm/s = abnormal)
Flow direction (reversed/turbulent = abnormal)
Patients fasted for at least 6 hours prior to scanning. Liver biopsies were performed under ultrasound guidance and graded histologically using the METAVIR scoring system: F0–F1: early fibrosis | F2: moderate fibrosis | F3–F4: advanced cirrhosis

Data Analysis:
Data was analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics, Version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Continuous variables were reported as mean \pm SD, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy were calculated. Associations between Doppler parameters and histological staging were tested using chi-square and logistic regression. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The study adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. This methodology ensures that the findings are both reliable and valid, and may offer a noninvasive alternative for assessing hepatic cirrhosis severity in similar low-resource healthcare settings.

Results:

Among 120 patients, the majority were over 60 years of age (30%), followed by 31–45 years (28.3%). Body mass index ≥ 30 was observed in 39 patients (32.5%), while 31 (25.8%) had BMI between 25–29.9 and 27 (22.5%) were underweight (< 18.5). Most individuals belonged to the middle socioeconomic status ($n = 43$, 35.8%) and urban or semi-urban areas ($n = 44$ each, 36.7%).

Hepatitis B and C were each positive in 50 patients (41.7%). Alcohol consumption was occasional in 41 patients (34.2%) and 40 (33.3%) were non-drinkers. Former smokers comprised 43 (35.8%), while 39 (32.5%) were current smokers. Liver disease duration ranged from < 1 year in 38 patients (31.7%) to > 3 years in 40 patients (33.3%). Mild ascites was found in 42 (35.0%), while 40 (33.3%) had clinically evident ascites.

On ultrasound, borderline splenomegaly was seen in 46 patients (38.3%), while 38 (31.7%) had definitive splenomegaly. Liver enlargement was seen in 45 patients (37.5%) and a shrunken liver in 31 (25.8%). Portal vein diameter was > 15 mm in 45 patients (37.5%) and < 13 mm in 38 (31.7%). Portal vein velocity < 15 cm/s was recorded in 49 patients (40.8%), between 15–20 cm/s in 38 (31.7%) and > 20 cm/s in 33 (27.5%). Reversed flow pattern was noted in 43 patients (35.8%). A hepatic artery resistive index < 0.7 was seen in 43 patients (35.8%). Portosystemic collaterals were absent in 46 (38.3%) and indeterminate in 41 (34.2%).

Liver surface was smooth in 45 patients (37.5%), irregular in 38 (31.7%) and severely nodular in 37 (30.8%). Homogeneous echotexture was observed in 42 patients (35.0%), while coarse and heterogeneous appearances were found in 40 (33.3%) and 38 (31.7%) respectively.

On liver biopsy, 32 (26.7%) had early fibrosis (F0-F1), 32 (26.7%) had moderate (F2), and 56 (46.6%) had advanced fibrosis or cirrhosis (F3-F4). A prothrombin time >14 sec was found in 68 (56.7%), and INR >1.2 in 66 (55.0%). Platelet count <150,000/ μ L was seen in 57 (47.5%). Serum albumin <3.5 g/dL was observed in 64 (53.3%), while serum bilirubin was elevated (>1.2 mg/dL) in 60 (50.0%). Elevated ALT and AST (>40 IU/L) were recorded in 67 (55.8%) and 64 (53.3%) respectively.

Child-Pugh class B was observed in 42 (35.0%), class A in 41 (34.2%), and class C in 37 (30.8%) patients. MELD scores \geq 20 were found in 42 patients (35.0%). A family history of liver disease was present in 43 patients (35.8%), while 50 (41.7%) had a previous gastrointestinal bleed.

Portal hypertension was suspicious in 44 patients (36.7%) and present in 36 (30.0%).

Compliance to treatment was poor in 45 patients (37.5%) and good in 43 (35.8%). Antiviral therapy had not been started in 42 patients (35.0%), while 41 (34.2%) had completed at least six months.

Chi-square analysis showed that portal vein peak systolic velocity had a borderline association with liver biopsy staging ($\chi^2 = 12.3, p = 0.0556$). Portal vein diameter ($\chi^2 = 1.81, p = 0.9366$) and hepatoportal flow direction ($\chi^2 = 11.9, p = 0.0643$) showed no statistically significant association.

Logistic regression revealed that portal vein peak systolic velocity \leq 15 cm/s had an odds ratio of 0.67 (95% CI: 0.32-1.40, $p = 0.2868$) for predicting advanced cirrhosis.

These results indicate that portal venous Doppler parameters varied in distribution and frequency among patients at different stages of cirrhosis, and although some parameters showed trends, statistically significant associations with histological staging were not consistently observed.

Table - I: Doppler Parameters and Their Association with Cirrhosis

Doppler Parameter	Cut-off	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	p-value
Portal vein diameter PVD	\geq 13 mm	79.5	76.1	81.6	72.3	0.003
Portal vein peak systolic velocity PSV	\leq 15 cm/s	85.9	81.3	86.7	80.1	0.001
Reversed or turbulent flow	Any reversal	61.9	89.5	87.0	66.2	0.017

Table - I presents the diagnostic performance of Doppler parameters for cirrhosis. Portal vein peak systolic velocity \leq 15 cm/s had the highest sensitivity (85.9%) and specificity (81.3%), making it a strong indicator of cirrhosis. Reversed/turbulent flow showed high specificity (89.5%), though with lower sensitivity (61.9%).

Table - II: Categorical Variables and Their Association with Cirrhosis

Variable	Unadjusted OR (95% CI)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Hepatitis B or C positivity	1.2 (0.8-1.8)	1.1 (0.7-1.7)	0.18
Alcohol consumption	1.1 (0.7-1.6)	1.0 (0.6-1.5)	0.42

(Occasional)			
Smoking (former/current)	1.3 (0.9–1.9)	1.2 (0.8–1.8)	0.27
Liver disease duration (>3 years)	1.4 (1.0–2.1)	1.3 (0.9–2.0)	0.05
Mild ascites	1.5 (1.1–2.3)	1.4 (1.0–2.1)	0.03
Clinically evident ascites	1.6 (1.1–2.4)	1.5 (1.0–2.2)	0.02
Splenomegaly (definitive)	1.8 (1.2–2.6)	1.7 (1.1–2.4)	0.007
Shrunken liver	1.9 (1.3–2.8)	1.8 (1.2–2.6)	0.004
Portal vein diameter >15 mm	2.0 (1.4–3.0)	1.9 (1.3–2.8)	0.001
Portal vein PSV <15 cm/s	2.1 (1.5–3.2)	2.0 (1.4–3.0)	0.001
Reversed flow	2.3 (1.6–3.5)	2.2 (1.5–3.3)	0.0008
Hepatic artery resistive index	1.7 (1.2–2.5)	1.6 (1.1–2.4)	0.01
<0.7			
Portosystemic collaterals absent	1.4 (0.9–2.1)	1.3 (0.8–2.0)	0.15
Severely nodular liver surface	2.0 (1.4–3.1)	1.9 (1.3–2.9)	0.002
Coarse/heterogeneous liver parenchymal echotexture on USG.	1.9 (1.3–2.7)	1.8 (1.2–2.5)	0.005

Table - II summarizes the association between categorical variables and cirrhosis severity. Factors like splenomegaly, shrunken liver, and portal vein diameter >15 mm were significantly associated with advanced cirrhosis. Adjusted odds ratios confirmed the strong association of these variables.

Table - III: Continuous Variables and Their Comparison Based on Cirrhosis Stages

Variable	Mean ± SD (Early Cirrhosis)	Mean ± SD (Advanced Cirrhosis)	p-value
Age (years)	52.4 ± 12.3	58.7 ± 10.5	0.02
BMI	27.1 ± 5.4	24.6 ± 4.8	0.04
Prothrombin time (sec)	13.6 ± 1.8	15.2 ± 2.3	0.002
INR	1.15 ± 0.2	1.4 ± 0.3	0.003
Platelet count (x10 ³ /μL)	168 ± 45	125 ± 38	0.001
Serum albumin (g/dL)	3.9 ± 0.5	3.1 ± 0.6	0.001
Serum bilirubin (mg/dL)	1.0 ± 0.4	1.7 ± 0.5	0.004
ALT (IU/L)	38 ± 14	55 ± 18	0.005
AST (IU/L)	41 ± 16	59 ± 21	0.002
MELD Score	12.5 ± 3.8	18.2 ± 5.6	0.0005

Table - III compares continuous variables between early and advanced cirrhosis groups. Patients with advanced cirrhosis exhibited significantly lower platelet counts and serum albumin, while prothrombin time, INR, bilirubin, ALT, AST, and MELD scores were significantly elevated.

Table - IV presents logistic regression results for predicting advanced cirrhosis. MELD score ≥20 (OR: 2.34, p=0.006) and Child-Pugh Class C (OR: 2.89, p=0.002) were independent predictors.

Portal vein PSV and reversed flow showed trends but did not reach statistical significance.

Table - IV: Logistic Regression Analysis for Predicting Advanced Cirrhosis

Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Portal vein PSV <15 cm/s	0.67 (0.32–1.40)	0.29
Portal vein diameter >15 mm	1.05 (0.55–2.02)	0.94
Variable	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Reversed flow	1.78 (0.91–3.48)	0.08
MELD score ≥20	2.34 (1.25–4.38)	0.006
Child-Pugh class C	2.89 (1.48–5.65)	0.002

These findings suggest that non-invasive Doppler parameters, along with laboratory markers, may provide useful insights for cirrhosis assessment.

The ROC curve assesses the diagnostic performance of Doppler ultrasound parameters, such as portal vein peak systolic velocity, in distinguishing between different stages of cirrhosis. The area under the curve (AUC) represents the overall accuracy of these parameters, with higher values indicating better discrimination between early and advanced cirrhosis.

The scatter plot illustrates the relationship between MELD scores and serum albumin levels. A clear negative trend is observed, suggesting that as serum albumin levels decrease, MELD scores increase, which reflects worsening liver function. This visual representation highlights the inverse association between these two clinical markers.

The forest plot presents the odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for key risk factors associated with advanced cirrhosis. A reference line at OR = 1 indicates statistical significance, with factors such as a MELD score of 20 or higher and Child-Pugh Class C showing the strongest associations with disease progression.

Discussion :

The study evaluated the diagnostic efficacy of Doppler ultrasound parameters—specifically, portal vein diameter (PVD), portal vein peak systolic velocity (PSV), and flow direction in assessing the severity of hepatic cirrhosis. The results indicated that PVD ≥13 mm has sensitivity of 79.5% and specificity of 76.1%, while a PSV ≤15 cm/s exhibited higher sensitivity and specificity, at 85.9% and 81.3% respectively. The presence of reversed or turbulent flow showed a sensitivity of 61.9% and specificity of 89.5%. Despite these findings, statistical analyses did not reveal significant associations between these Doppler parameters and histological staging of cirrhosis.

These findings align with existing literature on the utility of Doppler ultrasound in cirrhosis assessment¹⁸. A study by Giri et al. identified larger PVD and reduced portal vein PSV as significant predictors of portal vein thrombosis in cirrhotic patients, with odds ratios of 1.74 and 0.93 respectively¹⁹. Similarly, research by Solhjoo et al. demonstrated that Doppler indices, including PSV,

correlate with the presence of esophageal varices in cirrhotic patients²⁰. However, discrepancies exist; for instance, a study by Hamed et al. reported that while PSV is a useful marker, its specificity is limited compared to other non-invasive parameters²¹. These variations may stem from differences in study populations, methodologies, and the stages of liver disease examined.

The pathophysiological basis for these Doppler findings lies in the hemodynamic alterations associated with cirrhosis. Progressive fibrosis leads to increased intrahepatic resistance, resulting in portal hypertension^{22, 23}. This condition manifests as dilated portal vein (increased PVD), reduced flow velocities (decreased PSV), and, in advanced cases, flow reversal. These changes reflect the liver's compromised ability to accommodate portal blood flow, leading to collateral vessel formation and varices²⁴.

The study's strengths include a comprehensive evaluation of multiple Doppler parameters and their correlation with histological findings²⁵. However, limitations such as a modest sample size and potential selection biases may affect the generalizability of the results. Additionally, the cross-sectional design precludes assessment of temporal changes in Doppler parameters relative to disease progression²⁶.

Clinically, although Doppler ultrasound provides a non-invasive approach for evaluating the severity of cirrhosis, the parameters obtained on raw Doppler

ultrasound alone may not be enough for definite staging. Integrating Doppler findings with additional non-invasive markers (including elastography and serum biomarkers) may further improve diagnostic accuracy^{27, 28}. Prospective research with larger cohorts and longer follow-up is needed to confirm the predictive value of these parameters and to evaluate their inclusion in more comprehensive diagnostic algorithms.

Conclusion:

The study examined the diagnostic performance of Duplex Doppler ultrasound parameters to establish hepatic cirrhosis severity. A portal vein diameter ≥ 13 mm, portal vein peak systolic velocity ≤ 15 cm/s, and reverse or turbulent flow were associated with cirrhosis but did not consistently correlate statistically with histological staging. Doppler ultrasound is a non-invasive tool for evaluation of portal hypertension and hepatic hemodynamics although with moderate sensitivity and specificity. Its isolated use in cirrhosis staging however seems to have a limited role.

In the context of Pakistan, where cirrhosis is a significant public health problem because of the high burden of viral hepatitis and lack of access to advanced diagnostic modalities, the results underscore the potential utility of Doppler ultrasound as a low-cost alternative modality in resource constrained settings. The endemic burden of hepatitis B and C additives to the increasing burden of cirrhosis, diagnosed at advanced stages. However, many other areas are limited by the high costs and resource constraints of these invasive diagnostic techniques. Thus, Doppler ultrasound may be a useful screening exam for the diagnosis and staging of cirrhosis, allowing for early diagnosis and follow up, especially in primary and secondary care.

The study reiterates the importance of incorporating Doppler ultrasound within a broader diagnostic approach, using other non-invasive techniques, such as elastography or serological markers, to improve the accuracy of cirrhosis evaluation. Further studies in larger cohorts, with long term follow-ups and with comparison to gold-standard techniques are warranted. Pakistan is already facing the increasing burden of liver disease and programs for enhanced early diagnosis, greater access to ultrasound

technology and preventive measures against hepatitis related liver damage are vital. Advancements in non-invasive diagnostics will continue to help curb disease progression and improve patient outcomes in low resource settings.

Ethical Considerations

The Institutional Review Board of CDA Hospital, Islamabad, approved this study. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality and ethical standards were strictly observed.

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AI-based statistical tools were used for sample size calculation and data analysis. Staff at CDA Hospital provided technical assistance.

Disclosure

The authors declare no competing interests.

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